

Advance Phytochemical Screening of Active Phytocontents of *Linum Usitatissimum* and *Guizotia Abyssinica* Plant Seeds in Spectrometry a Study of Comparative Properties

M.K. Ghorase, G.P. Sahu
Department of Chemistry,
Govt. J. H. P. G. College Betul

S.K. Udaipure
Department of Chemistry,
Govt. N. M. V. College Narmadapuram

Abstract: Many plant species used in the treatment of different diseases. Plant derived active compound have played an important role in the development of clinically useful agents. *Guizotia abyssinica* and *Linum usitatissimum* plant seeds are used for many disease treatments. Aim of the present study is investigate the phytochemical analysis of Methanol, petroleum ether, Chloroform and Acetone extracts of *linum usitatissimum* and *Guizotia abyssinica* plants by spectrometry like UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectrometry. Qualitative analysis of phytochemical Screening reveals the presence of Phenol, Saponins, Alkaloids, Protein and Carbohydrates. Current research describes a simple, effective and reproducible Comparative phytochemical analysis of natural seeds.

Keywords:- Medicinal plants, Phytochemicals, *Guizotia abyssinica*, *Linum usitatissimum*, Spectrometry, Antioxidant activity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Plants produce an amazing variety of metabolites that are gaining importance for their therapeutic and biotechnological applications. Plants have been an important Source of medicine for thousands of years. Plants are the source of many modern medicine. Phytochemicals are responsible for the healing properties of plants. Plants turn out many secondary metabolites together with flavonoids, Alkaloids, Steroids, Saponins, terpenoids and glycosides to safeguard themselves from the attack of present infectious agent, insects, pest and environmental stresses.[1]

Niger (*Guizotia abyssinica*) is an oil seed plant cultivated for over 5000 years. It is widely grown in Southern India and Ethiopia. In India, it is cultivated on the slopes of hills and plains along the coasts of Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Odessa, Maharashtra, Bihar, Karnataka, and West Bengal. *G. abyssinica* dicotyledonous plant, medium to fine branches, growing up to 2 m high. The plant grows very well in poorly drained, heavy clay soils. An important feature of this plant is that it provides good seed yield even under poor growing conditions. Niger is heavily cultivated for the extraction of Oil used for soap, lighting, lubrication and used as biodiesel. Niger oil absorbs the fragrance of flowers used as a base oil in the perfume industry. The plant is used in various Indian

communities for the treatment of rheumatism, rheumatoid arthritis and infectious diseases.[2]

Flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) plant growing to one m tall. The seeds are oval, 2.5-9.5 cm long and 1-3.5 cm. thin shiny in experienced depilatory with a black and a brief stalk regarding are 1-1.8 cm long seeds of *Linum usitatisamum* plant are used medication for treatment of Rheumatism, Dyspepsia, stomach upset, Dysmenorrheal, Diabetes, Cardiovascular disease, Cancer, Expelling disorders, Skin diseases, Trauma symptom and has sedative and antiviral properties. The seeds and alternative Components of *Linum usitatissimum* plant periwinkle exhibit inhibitor properties. Therefore, phenoplast compounds have chemical reaction properties that act as reducing agents, chemical element donors. It's multiple applications in foods, cosmetics and Pharmaceutical industries. Besides inhibitor activity, these compounds exhibit antiallergic, medicinal drug, antimicrobial antithrombotic cardio protecting and vasodilatory effects.[3]

Phytochemicals are basically divided into two groups of Primary and secondary metabolites based on the activity of plant metabolism. Primary or basic metabolites include regular carbohydrates, amino acids, proteins and chlorophyll while secondary metabolites include alkaloids, saponins, Steroids, flavonoids, tannins and more.[4]

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Collection of Samples:

Guizotia abyssinica and *Linum usitatissimum* are collected from forest region of Betul, M.P., India were Collected in the winter season and summer season. The plants calibrated taxonomically and was preserved for extraction.

B. Preparation of Solvent Extracts of plants

Guizotia abyssinica seeds were properly cleaned with running water then properly removed with purified water. The Seeds dried for 5 days at ambient temperature for shade. Second, dried seeds were coarsely used with a mortar and pestle and then a mechanical blender was used to ground them further. 30gm 340 ml of organic Solution of Methanol & D.W. were collected from the sample extraction at Soxhlet. The extraction was completed in 8 days at 65°C. In order to form a paste, extract were then

evaporated at 45°C and further transfer to sterile and refrigerated once used. [5][6]

Linum usitatissimum seeds were properly washed with running water then purified water. The Seeds dried and crushed to urge powder. Dried powder of seeds 50gm was hot extracted with 500 cc fuel exploitation soxhlet instrumentation. [7]The Soxheletion at 30°C was done for one week to obtain extract. The extract was evaporated in water bath at 70°C to obtain Crude for phytochemical analysis. Once the entire evaporation, the load of the extracts was recorded and so labeled.[8] The extractions stored separately at 4°C in air tight battle. After dried powder 50gm cold extracted with 200ml Petroleum Ether using rotary shaker and were incubated for 1 week at 25°C at least 5 times vibration per day.[9]The extract were filtered exploitation textile material and volatilized exploitation rotary distillation instrumentation, this extract dried in 50°C oven for 24 hours and finally kept at 4°C temperature.[10]

C. Identification tests for Phytochemical Constituents.

Phytochemical analysis was performed to determine the presence of bioactive Compounds like carbohydrates, proteins, starch, amino acids, steroids, glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, tanning, Saponins, Phenols and resins by the following procedure [11]

a) Test for Alkaloids

5ml of the prepared extracts were volatilized to standing. The residue was taken in 5 ml of acid, saturated with chemical compound and filtered. The filtrate was one by one tested with following reagents:

- **Wagner's Test**

To few ml of each of the sample solution, Wagner's reagent (iodine in potassium iodide) was added, which resulted in the formation of reddish brown precipitate indicating the presence of alkaloids.

- **Mayer's Test**

To 1ml of each of the sample solution few drops of Mayer's reagent (Potassium mercuric chloride solution) was added. Formation of cream white precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

b) Test For Phenols.

To the crude extract 2ml of 2% ferric chloride solution was added and black coloration was formed for the presence of phenols.

c) Test for flavonoid

To 4cc of extract add 1.5cc 50% methanol solution. The solution was heat and metal chemical element was further to this solution, 5-6 drops of centered HCl was further, red color made up our minds for flavonoids and Orange color for flavones.

d) Test for Quinones

About 0.5 gm of plant extract was taken and extra 1 c.c. of extract and 1 cc of con. H₂SO₄ was extract formation of red color shows the presence of quinones. One drop of ethanol take a look at resolution is placed on a filter paper, followed by one drop of 0.2% ethanolic phenylacetone nitrile resolution and one drop of 0.1 N hydroxide. A positive response is indicated by the appearance of a blue or violet stain edged by a yellow ring.

e) Test for terpenoids (Salkowski Test)

5cc of each extract was mixed during a try of cc of Chloroform and con. H₂SO₄ (3ml) was strictly extra to create a layer. A brown coloration of the bury face was intentional to indicate positive results for the presence of terpenoids.

f) Test for Tannins:

To 5ml of extract, few drops of 5% ferric chloride solution were added. The appearance of violet indicates the presence of Saponins.

g) Test for saponins

To 0.5 ml of filtrate, added 5ml of distilled water and shaken vigorously for a stable persistence froth. Frothing which persisted on warming indicates the presence of saponins.

h) Test for Steroids.

To a 3 cc of extract add a 3 cc Chloroform and 3 cc of con. H₂SO₄ shake well; chloroform 1 layer show chromatic color light.

i) Test for Fatty Acids.

About 0.5 ml of extract was mixed 5 ml of ether. The extract was allowed to evaporate, on filter paper and dried. The appearance of transparence on filter paper indicates the presence of fatty acids.

j) Test For Carbohydrates

For 2ml test solution added 2 drop of the molisch's reagents (a solution of α -naphthol in 95% ethanol). Therefore solution is then poured slowly in to a tube containing 2 cc of center red vitriol So 2 layers kind. Purple to ruby violet color at the junction of 2 layers indicates the presence of macromolecule.

k) Test for Glycosides

To the solution of the extract add glacial carboxylic acid, few drops baseball metal Chloride and 1cc red vitriol further and determined for a brown coloration at the junction of two layers and additionally the bluish in experienced colorize the upper layer.

l) Test for Proteins.

a) Xanthoprotein Test

The extracts are treated with a few drops of Con.HNO₃; the yellow color indicates the presence of protein

m) Check Amino Acids.

a) Ninhydrin Test

In 1ml of boiled sample with a 0.1% acetone solution of ninhydrin, the appearance of pink indicates the presence of amino acids.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• Observations:

S.N.	Phytochemical Constituents	Guizotia abyssinica	Linum usitatissimum
1.	Alkaloids	+ve	+ve
2.	Flavonoids	+ve	+ve
3.	Phenolics	+ve	+ve
4.	Terpenoids	+ve	+ve
5.	Saponins	+ve	+ve
6.	Fatty acids	+ve	+ve
7.	Glycosides	+ve	+ve
8.	Carbohydrates	-ve	-ve
9.	Proteins	+ve	+ve
10.	Amino Acids	+ve	+ve

Table 1: Phytochemical Screening of extract of Guizotia abyssinica and Linum usitatissimum

Fig.1: FTIR Spectrum of *Linum usitatissimum* plant seeds extract

The FTIR analysis confirms the presence of unsaturated fatty acid ester due to the presence of bands of 3010 cm, 1715 cm, 1645 cm and 1240 cm, these and the other bands are also reported in other research. The band at 1735 cm refers to the stretching of the ester carbonyl and the

band at 1240 cm to the stretching of the CO bond. Moreover, the bands at 3010 cm and 1645 cm are attributed to the double bonds present in the chains as can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 2: FTIR Spectrum of *Guizotia abyssinica* plant seeds extract

The FTIR analysis confirms the presence of unsaturated fatty acid ester due to the presence of bands of 3436 cm, 1174 cm, 1239 cm and 1285 cm, these and the other bands are also reported in other research. The band at

1726 cm refers to the stretching of the ester carbonyl and the band at 1285 cm to the stretching of the CO bond. Moreover, the bands at 3436 cm is attributed to the double bonds present in the chains as can be seen in Figure 2.

¹H-NMR spectrum of *Linum usitatissimum* and *Guizotia abyssinica* seed extract

Fig. 3 : ¹H-NMR spectrum of *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract at 400 MHz in CDCl₃

The ¹H-NMR spectra of *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract, shown in Figure 3, show the number of protons at each chemical shift with different acyl groups. The spectral signals are attributed to the presence of protons in triglycerol and the area of each chemical shift is related to that of *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract before and after enrichment. It can be seen that the proton count at each chemical shift is the same except for the unsaturated region (5.2–5.3 ppm) and the chemical shift at 2.3 ppm, which indicated that the fatty acid composition of *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract enrichment is similar. Similar

observations are observed in section 3.1, as described in the Materials and Methods section, fatty acid composition calculated using 1 second H-NMR spectra (Andrade et al., 2011) and linolenic acid. The iodine value was calculated by ¹H-NMR analysis with the Hunas method (IV = 10.54 + 13.39 *% olefinic protons in the lineages). IS. oil), and turns out to be 169.3 grams of I₂ / 100 grams of *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract. From the results of the study. Reported in section 3.6. Therefore, enriched *Linum usitatissimum* seed extract can be a potential supplement for food, pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Shalini S. And Sampathkumar P. (2012) Phytochemical screening and anti microbial activity of plant extracts
- [2.] Mohan Kumar BN, Basavegowda, Vyakaranahal BS, Deshpande VK, Kenchanagoudar PV. Influence of sowing dates on production of seed yield in niger (*Guizotia abyssinica* Cass.). Karnataka J Agric Sci, 2011; 24(3):289–93.
- [3.] Xing, L., Zhao, F.-M., Cao, Y.-F., Wang, M., Mei, S., Li, S.-P., Cai, Z.-Y., 2014. Principal component analysis of mineral elements and fatty acids composition in flaxseed from ten different regions. Spectrosc. Spectr. Anal. 34(9), 2538–2543.
- [4.] Savithramma N, Linga Rao M, Suhrulatha D. Screening of medicinal plants for secondary metabolites. Middle East J Sci Res, 2011; 8(3):579-84
- [5.] Jigna P, Sumitra CV. In vitro antimicrobial activity and phytochemical analysis of some Indian medicinal plants. Turk J Biol, 2007; 31: 53-8.
- [6.] Bhumi G, Savithramma N. Screening of pivotal medicinal plants for qualitative and quantitative phytochemical constituents. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci, 2014; 6: 63-5.
- [7.] Kumari K. and Gupta S. (2013) Phytopotential of *Linum usitatissimum* plant us L.(G.) Don. Var. International Journal of Research in Pure and Applied Microbiology, 3(3):77-82
- [8.] Govindasamy C. and Srinivasan R. (2012) In vitro antibacterial activity and phytochemical analysis of *Linum usitatissimum* (Linn.) G. Don. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine, S155-158
- [9.] Yaqoob, N., Bhatti, I.A., Anwar, F., Mushtaq, M., Artz, W. E., 2016. Variation in physicochemical/analytical characteristics of oil among different flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) cultivars. Ital. J. Food Sci. 28 (1), 83–89.
- [10.] Wang, H., Wang, J.H., Qiu, C.S., Ye, Y.T., Guo, X.B., Chen, G., Li, T., Wang, Y.F., Fu, X., Liu, R.H., 2017. Comparison of phytochemical profiles and health benefits in fiber and oil flaxseeds (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). Food Chem. 214, 227–233.
- [11.] Yadav RNS, Agarwala M. Phytochemical analysis of some medicinal plants. J Phytol, 2011; 3(12): 10-4.
- [12.] Xie, D.W., Dai, Z.G., Yang, Z.M., Tang, Q., Deng, C.H., Xu, Y., Wang, J., Chen, J., Zhao, D.B., Zhang, S.L., Zhang, S.Q., Su, J.G., 2019. Combined genome-wide association analysis and transcriptome sequencing to identify candidate genes for flax seed fatty acid metabolism. Plant Sci. 286, 98–107.
- [13.] Zhang, J.P., Xie, Y.P., Dang, Z., Wang, L.M., Li, W.J., Zhao, W., Zhao, L., Dang, Z.H., 2016. Oil content and fatty acid components of oilseed flax under different environments in China. Agron. J. 108 (1), 365–372.
- [14.] Rajwade, A.V., Kadoo, N.Y., Borikar, S.P., Harsulkar, A.M., Ghorpade, P.B., Gupta, V.S., 2014. Differential transcriptional activity of SAD, FAD2 and FAD3 desaturase genes in developing seeds of flax seed contribute to varietal variation in alpha-linolenic acid content. Phytochemistry 98, 41–53.
- [15.] Sain M. and Sharma V. (2013) *Linum usitatissimum* plant: A Review of Potential Therapeutic Properties. Int. J. Pure App. Biosci. 1(6): 139-142
- [16.] Baghel S, Bansal YK. Synergistic effect of BAP and GA3 on in vitro flowering of *Guizotia abyssinica* Cass.-a multipurpose oil crop. Physiol Mol Biol Plants, 2014; 20(2): 241–47.
- [17.] Baghel S, Bansal YK. Micropropagation and in vitro flowering of a biodiesel plant niger *Guizotia abyssinica* (Cass.). Asian J Exp Biol Sci, 2013; 4(4): 532-39.
- [18.] Kiran Kumari SP, Sridevi V, Chandana Lakshmi MVV. Studies on phytochemical screening of aqueous extract collected from fertilizers affected two medicinal plants. J Chem Biol Phys Sci, 2012; 2(3):1326-32.
- [19.] Ramadan MF. Functional properties, nutritional value, and industrial applications of niger oilseeds (*Guizotia abyssinica* Cass.). Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr, 2012; 52:1-8.
- [20.] Sarin R, Sharma M, Khan A. Studies on *Guizotia abyssinica* L. oil: biodiesel synthesis and process optimization. Bioresour Technol, 2009; 100: 4187-92.